

POLITENESS IN CHINESE

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Named after Mirzo Ulug'bek

As the saying goes: "良言一句三冬暖，恶语伤人六月寒 A good word will warm the winter three times, and a bad word will hurt others and the June cold." Polite words are among the good words. Polite language plays a very important role in public relations activities.

There used to be an ancient saying in China that "君子不失色于人，不失口于人 a gentleman never loses his looks to others, nor loses his words to others", which means that a virtuous person should be polite to others, not rude or rude. Treating people politely and using polite language are fine traditions of Chinese nation.

Politeness and etiquette are codes of conduct for people to show respect and friendship to each other in frequent interactions. Polite language is a concrete manifestation of respect for others and a stepping stone to friendly relations. Therefore, it is very important for us to use polite language in our daily life, especially in social situations. Saying more polite words not only shows respect for others, but also shows that you are self-cultivated; so using more polite words is not only conducive to a harmonious atmosphere between the two parties, but also beneficial to communication.

The polite words "谢谢 thank you", "对不起 excuse me" and "请 please", if used properly, can play an unexpected role in reconciling and harmonious interpersonal relationships.

No matter how little help someone gives you, you should say "谢谢 thank you" sincerely. Using the word "thank you" correctly will make your language full of charm

and make the other party feel warm. Pay attention to the other person's reaction when thanking you. When the other party feels at a loss about your gratitude, you should explain to him the reasons for your thanks in concise language. Thank others for their thanks, and the thanks can be answered with "没事儿 it's nothing, 不客气 you're welcome", "我乐意帮你 I'm happy to help", and "应该的 should".

Learning to apologize to people in social situations is a panacea for easing the tension that may arise between the two parties. For example, if you step on someone else's foot on the bus, saying "对不起 I'm sorry" can resolve the other person's unhappiness. The most important thing when apologizing is to have sincerity. Don't make excuses first when apologizing, as if you are shirking responsibility. At the same time, you must pay attention to apologizing in a timely manner. If you hesitate, you will lose the opportunity to apologize. When you need annoying help on a foreign-related occasion, saying "对不起, 你能替我把茶水递过来吗 I'm sorry, can you pass me the tea" can reflect a person's humility and self-cultivation.

"请 Please" is a polite word that must be on the lips almost whenever you need to trouble others. Such as "请问 excuse me", "请原谅 forgive me", "请留步 please stay", "请用餐 please have a meal", "请指教 please give advise me", "请稍等 please wait", "请关照 please take care" and so on. Frequent use of the word "请 please" will make the words tactful and polite, which is the best way to lower one's position and elevate the other party's position more naturally. There are a lot of versions the using polite words in Chinese, one of them is daily words. For example:

Ten words of polite language: "您好 Hello, 请 please, 对不起 sorry, 谢谢 thank you, 再见 goodbye".

Greeting words: "早上好 Good morning", "下午好 Good afternoon", "晚上好 Good evening", "您好 Hello", "很高兴认识你 Nice to meet you", "请多指教 Please give advise", "请多关照 Please take care of me", etc.

Appreciation words: "谢谢 Thank you", "苏驾 Excuse me", "让您费心了 Thank you for your trouble", "实在过意不去 I'm really sorry", "拜托了 Please", "麻烦您 Trouble you", "感谢您的帮助 Thank you for your help", etc.

To disturb or apologize to the other party: "对不起 I'm sorry", "请原谅 Please forgive me", "很抱歉 I'm sorry", "请稍等 Please wait a moment", "麻烦 Trouble", "请多包涵 Please forgive me", etc.

When accepting the other party's thanks and apology: "别客气 You're welcome", "不用谢 You're welcome", "不客气 You're welcome", "没关系 It's okay", "请不要放在心上 Please don't take it to heart", etc.

Farewell words: "再见 Goodbye", "欢迎下次再来 Welcome again next time", "请慢走 Walk slowly", "祝你一路顺风 Wish you all the best", "请下次再来 Please come again", etc.

Avoided words: "喂 Hey", "不知道 I don't know", "笨蛋 Idiot", "你不懂 You don't understand", "猪脑 pig head" and so on.

你能。。。&请给 Can you pass me...? vs Give me...

People don't like others to dictate what they do, so sometimes getting what you want straight away can be tricky. Replace commands that sound like "Give me the newspaper" with "Can you pass me the newspaper?"

你能给我。。。&滚! Could you give me five minutes? vs Go away.

You are very busy at work, but your co-workers ask you for help. . . Just saying "滚 Go away" is definitely inappropriate when you're too busy at work to do anything else. Instead, use phrases like "你能给我五分钟吗? Could you give me five minutes?"

不好意思&让开! Excuse me. vs Move.

Telling someone to "让开 Move out of the way" sounds extremely rude and is likely to get rejected. The next time someone is in your way, you can say "不好意思 Excuse me" and avoid an unpleasant situation and get the results you expect!

恐怕，不行&不！ I'm afraid I can't. vs No.

Sometimes it is very difficult to decline a friend's invitation. Just saying "不 No" sounds rude. The next time you want to say no without offending someone, say, "恐，不行 I'm afraid I can't."

The choice of appropriate polite language on the phone can make or break a conversation more effectively. If someone calls for someone, don't say, "等 Wait". Instead, politely ask "请稍等 Can you hold, please?/Hold on, please."

In conversation, be sure to use polite language more kindly. Commonly used polite words include "请 please", "谢谢 thank you", "对不起 excuse me", "喂 hello", "拜托 please", "麻烦您 please", "没事儿吗？ is it okay", "您觉得怎么样？ what do you think" and so on. At the same time, different polite words can be selected according to the different meanings expressed in polite words.

In short, as a special and universal social and cultural phenomenon, polite language occupies an important position in social communication, especially in international communication. It is better to study the pragmatic differences of polite language in English and Chinese. Help us understand the Western thinking style and cultural background, thereby reducing and avoiding pragmatic barriers caused by pragmatic differences, achieving the purpose of smooth communication and pleasant cooperation. At the same time, it is also more conducive to spreading Chinese culture to the world.

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